

EOSC-ENTRUST Kick-off meeting

18 & 19 March 2024, Amsterdam

Slides

Funded by
the European Union

EOSC-ENTRUST Kick Off Meeting

18 & 19 March 2024

Introduction

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Agenda 18 March

12:30-13:30	Welcome, introductions & working lunch	Peter Maccallum (ELIXIR)
13:30-13:50	Introduction to EOSC-ENTRUST & coordination team and opening mentimeter	Peter Maccallum & Juan Arenas (ELIXIR)
13.50-14.10	Trusted environments for sensitive data management in EOSC	Peter Szegedi (DG RTD)
14:10-15:40	A Trusted research environment blueprint <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • WP13 Trusted research environment blueprint • WP16 Trusted researcher identities and data authorisation • WP19 RO-Crate and workflow processing 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Stefan Negru (CSC) & Sushma Grellscheid (ELIXIR NO) • Ludek Matyska (MUNI) • Laia Codó (BSC) & Phil Quinlan (UNOTT)
15.40-16.10	Break	
16.10-16.30	Examples & ecosystem <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • SATRE • NORTRE 	Moderator: Peter Maccallum (ELIXIR) <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • SATRE - Christian Cole (HDR-UK, DARE, ELIXIR-UK) • NORTRE - Anne Bergsaker (UiO)
16.30-17.15	WP7 Drivers: Validating blueprints across Governance domains <i>10 min presentation: objectives, work plan for next 6 months & connections to other WPs & 2 min pitch per Driver. Followed by a discussion on requirements definitions for MVP</i>	Jan-Willem Boiten (Health-RI & Drivers)
17:15-18:00	WP10 TRE Provider Forum <i>10 min presentations: objectives, work plan for next 6 months & connections to other WPs. Followed by a discussion on requirements definitions for MVP</i>	Heidi Laine (EUDAT & Providers)
18.00	Wrap up day 1, closing mentimeter, group photo and opening of networking reception	Peter Maccallum (ELIXIR)

18:15-20:30

Networking Reception

Agenda 19 March

9.00-9.20	EOSC partnership	Ute Gunsenheimer (EOSC-A)
9.20-10.20	TITAN, SIESTA & EOSC-ENTRUST <i>10 min presentations of TITAN & SIESTA, followed by a panel discussion</i>	Moderator: Emily Jefferson (HDR-UK) Panel discussion: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • SIESTA - Alvaro Lopez (IFCA Santander) - online • TITAN - Antonio Skarmeta (UMU) - online • EOSC-ENTRUST - Jonathan Tedds (ELIXIR) • EOSC Partnership - Ute Gunsheimer (EOSC-A)
10.20-11.00	EOSC-ENTRUST strategic alignment & outreach <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • WP1 Project coordination and strategic alignment • WP4 Communication, Dissemination & Outreach <i>10 min presentations: objectives, work plan for next 6 months & connections to other WPs. Discussion.</i>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Jonathan Tedds (ELIXIR), ELIXIR PMO, Sara Garavelli (EUDAT) • Elaine Harrison (ELIXIR), Paola Quattroni (HDR-UK)
11.00-11.30	Break	
11:30-11:50	HE Reporting	Enrico Pellizari (PO) - online
11:50-12:10	Project Governance	ELIXIR PMO
12:10-12.30	Closing remarks & next events	Peter Maccallum, ELIXIR
12.30-13.30	Working lunch	

EOSC-ENTRUST Coordination Team

Peter Maccallum (Project Coordinator)
ELIXIR Chief Technical Officer

Jonathan Tedds (Scientific Coordinator)
ELIXIR Programme Manager for Scientific
Computing & EOSC Coordinator

Maria Tyler (From May-2024)
ELIXIR Senior Project manager

Maria Dolores (Mado) Fernandez
ELIXIR Project manager

Juan Arenas Márquez (interim)
ELIXIR Head of Project Management Office &
European Genomic Data Infrastructure Lead

Contact the coordinator : Eosc-entrust-coordination@elixir-europe.org

EOSC-ENTRUST - our project

The mission of EOSC-ENTRUST is

- to create a European network of trusted research environments for sensitive data

...and...

- to drive European interoperability by joint development of a common blueprint for federated data access and analysis.

Objectives (1,2)

EOSC-ENTRUST aims to create a tightly knit network of nationally operated and governed TREs capable of supporting large-scale European research...

- **Objective 1:** Create a **European network of Trusted Research Environments**, linked to EOSC and EuroHPC, to enable transnational collaborative research on sensitive or restricted data.
- **Objective 2:** Trusted Research Environment providers implement, validate, and promote their capabilities through a **European framework using common standards and shared legal, operational and technical language**.

Objectives (3,4)

EOSC-ENTRUST aims to create a tightly knit network of nationally operated and governed TREs capable of supporting large-scale European research...

- **Objective 3: National funders and governments understand the network of TRE capabilities** serving their needs, and how TREs support their national priorities and their contributions to selected transnational programmes.
- **Objective 4:** The European Network of Trusted Research Environments (ENTRUST) is embedded in the **European Open Science Cloud** and the **European Data Spaces** and fosters an ecosystem of public, private and joint-venture providers of TRE services.

Ambition

We will take European research beyond the State of the Art...

- ...in European collaboration: a European network of Trusted Research Environments (TREs) **expands EOSC's access to resources and valuable data sets** for research.
- ...in European connectivity: delivering **a Blueprint for connecting TREs into large-scale networks** for federated data via a standard set of methods.
- ...in FAIR data workflows: secure and reproducible **cross-TRE analysis** of sensitive data.
- ...in European HPC: pilot **inclusion of EuroHPC sites** into the TRE network

Partners

Barcelona Supercomputing Center - Centro Nacional de Supercomputacion	EMBL-EBI	Sciensano	University of Essex
Bielefeld University	EUDAT Collaborative data infrastructure	Sigma2 AS	University of Ljubljana
BioData.pt	Finnish Institute for Health and Welfare (Terveyden ja hyvinvoinnin laitos)	Stichting Health-RI	University of Nottingham
Centre for Genomic Regulation (CRG)	GESIS - Leibniz-Institut für Sozialwissenschaften	SURF	University of Oslo
CESSDA ERIC	GRNET – National Infrastructures for Research and Technology	Tárki Alapítvány	University of Tartu
CSC – Tieteen tietotekniikan keskus Oy	Health Data Research UK (HDR UK)	The University of Manchester	Uppsala universitet
Danmarks Tekniske Universitet(DTU)	Luxembourg National Data Service (LNDS)	Turku University of Applied Sciences (Turun ammattikorkeakoulu)	Vlaams Instituut voor Biotechnologie (VIB)
ECRIN (European Clinical Research Infrastructure Network)	Masaryk University	University of Bergen	VSB - Technical University of Ostrava
ELIXIR	NTNU - Norwegian University of Science and Technology	University of Dundee	

Drivers

A portfolio of Multidisciplinary Drivers informs and validates the blueprint.

- Driver 1: **Federated Human Genomics** as a catalyst for European TRE provision
- Driver 2: Common standards to enable trans-national sharing of **administrative/register and social science data**
- Driver 3: Enabling secure transnational re-use of **clinical research data** in a legally and ethically compliant manner
- Driver 4: **Public-Private interactions** between TRE in health and environmental data

Partners - as Drivers

Barcelona Supercomputing Center - Centro Nacional de Supercomputacion	EMBL-EBI	Sciensano	University of Essex
Bielefeld University	EUDAT Collaborative data infrastructure	Sigma2 AS	University of Ljubljana
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Provider Forum

TRE Providers Forum consolidate existing expertise and good practices for the common interoperability blueprint.

Partners - as Providers

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Architecture & Technologies

Blueprint architecture for composable TREs - and beyond the state of the art in some foundational technologies:

- **Trusted research environment blueprint** - will gather the requirements and build a roadmap for a blueprint that enables an interoperable network of TRE services in Europe.
- **Trusted researcher identities and data authorisation** - will deal with the need of higher trust in the authentication and authorization in the TREs context.
- **RO-Crate and workflow processing** - the combination of RO-Crates and workflows provides the interoperability framework and execution approach for practical pan-TRE analysis.

eosc

European Context and Data Spaces

Communication and Outreach
WP4, 5, 6

A note on the 'EOSC-ENTRUST' year

The Work Plan is designed to give us an iterative annual development cycle:

- **March General Assemblies** - we have just two in person, one Kick-Off and one at the end. The others will be online only.
- **May Requirements and Capabilities workshops** - to assess the ENTRUST baseline/SOA and measure adoption
- **November Evaluation & Adoption workshops** - to showcase the development of the blueprint & technologies
- **January, October EOSC calendar** - EOSC will run a Winter School and an autumn Symposium - the best dissemination forum for our outputs

What to do next

Collaborative minutes

[Collaborative Minutes](#)

Any doubts:

Eosc-entrust-coordination@elixir-europe.org or in [slack](#)

How I access the project information

[EOSC-ENTRUST Project repository](#)

I (or people from my organisation) don't have access

[Registration from](#)

Where is the final project set to do

[Project part B](#)

What is your institution responsible for and when

[Deliverables and Milestones](#)

How a lump sum grant is different from a standard EC grant:

[Lump Sum EC guidance](#)

What is happening in the project

[Project calendar](#) in [Ical](#)

ENTRUST

European Network of Trusted
Research Environments

 www.eosc-entrust.eu

 [@eosc-entrust](https://twitter.com/eosc-entrust)

 [/company/eosc-entrust](https://www.linkedin.com/company/eosc-entrust)

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NORTRE

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OF OSLO

 NTNU

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 eOSC | ENTRUST

European Network of Trusted Research Environments

NORWEGIAN TRUSTED RESEARCH ENVIRONMENTS

- The Norwegian ministry of health's national Health Analysis Platform (HAP)
- NORTRE= Services for sensitive data (TSD) + Hunt Cloud + Safe
- Collaboration between University of Oslo (UiO), University of Bergen (UiB) and Norwegian university of Science and Technology (NTNU)
- Secure storage and analysis with federated trust between platforms
- Simplify data movement between platforms
- Interoperability between platforms

SHARING

THE DIFFERENT PLATFORMS

 NTNU | HUNT Cloud

TSD

UNIVERSITY
OF OSLO

- 8000 users, over 1800 active research projects
- 90 institutions
- Secure login
- Scalable storage
- Virtual machine
- HPC
- Databases
- Survey solution
- Apps
- APIs

TSD - SOFTWARE

UNIVERSITY
OF OSLO

HUNT Cloud

<https://docs.hdc.ntnu.no>

 NTNU | HUNT Cloud

*Grab your compass
Grab your map
Here be uncharted
waters
Here be dragons
But in the distance
The joyous unknown*

Slides: Signe Elisabeth Åsberg, strategic account manager HUNT Cloud

Balance creativity and control

HUNT Workbench

HUNT Workbench provides you with web-based access to modern data science tools such as Jupyter Notebooks, Python, RStudio, R and MATLAB.

The screenshot shows the HUNT Workbench Launcher interface. At the top, there is a navigation bar with menu items: File, Edit, View, Run, Kernel, Git, Tabs, Settings, Help, Documentation, Control Panel, and Logout. Below this is a search bar labeled "Filter files by name" and a file browser showing a directory structure with folders like "archive", "scratch", "work", and a file "README.L...". The main area is titled "Launcher" and contains two sections: "Notebook" and "Console". The "Notebook" section displays a grid of icons for various environments: Python 3 (ipykernel), Glances, MATLAB Kernel, Open MATLAB, pgweb, Python [conda env:conda-], R [conda env:conda-r], RStudio, and VS Code. The "Console" section displays a grid of icons for: Python 3 (ipykernel), MATLAB Kernel, Python [conda env:conda-], and R [conda env:conda-r]. The interface is clean and modern, with a light gray background and clear icons.

SAFE

UNIVERSITY
OF BERGEN

- 500 projects, 1800 users, from UiB and outside
- Secure login
- Scalable storage and compute
- Virtual machine
- Import and export of data between outside and project
- Secure video capture

eOSC | ENTRUST

European Network of Trusted Research Environments

THANKS

EOSC-ENTRUST Kick Off Meeting

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A trusted research environment blueprint

Funded by
the European Union

UK Health Data Research Alliance, & NHSX. (2021). Building Trusted Research Environments - Principles and Best Practices; Towards TRE ecosystems (1.0). Zenodo.
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5767586>

Author includes Tim Hubbard, Director of ELIXIR

A trusted research environment blueprint

1. WP5abc Trusted research environment blueprint
2. WP6abc Trusted researcher identities and data authorisation
3. WP7abc RO-Crate and workflow processing

10 min presentations on objectives, tasks, deliverables & milestones, effort overview, links with other WPs, Planning M1-6. Followed by a discussion on the minimal viable product.

WP5abc Trusted research environment blueprint

Lead: CSC & UiB

Partners: SURF, HDR-UK, BSC, MU, UNIVDUN

10-min overview of WP 5abc:

- Objectives
- Tasks
- Deliverables & Milestones
- Effort overview
- Links with other WPs
- Planning Months 1-6

TRE Blueprint - objectives

5A - Establishing a baseline and roadmap

- ❖ Coordinate and conduct the blueprint requirements gathering and establish a baseline analysis of existing TRE services capabilities
- ❖ Define requirements for an interoperable and scalable network of TRE services, covering technical, legal, organisational and semantic aspects of EOSC Interoperability Framework as relevant.

5B - Development and validation

- ❖ Coordinate and conduct the blueprint development
- ❖ Build TRE services' interoperability by creating recommendations on unified policies, establish a baseline understanding of TRE services' security according to Five safes principles and develop common risk mitigation strategies

5C - Demonstrating impact & building the network

- ❖ Compile and publish the blueprint
- ❖ Demonstrate the impact of the blueprint.

TRE Blueprint - Objectives

TRE Blueprint - Tasks

5A Establishing a baseline and roadmap

T5A.1 TRE services capabilities baseline analysis for the blueprint

T5A.2 Requirements and roadmap to the blueprint

5B Development and validation

T5B.1 Reference TRE service architecture for the blueprint

T5B.2 Validate selected blueprint recommendations for TRE network interoperability

T5B.3 Recommendations for TRE services policy alignment

5C Demonstrating impact & building the network

T5C.1 Compiling the blueprint for building an interoperable TRE services

T5C.2 Service catalog for interoperable TRE services network

TRE Blueprint - Deliverables

EOSC ENTRUST		2024										2025										2026										2027											
Calendar Month		3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12	1	2						
WP#	Project month	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12	13	14	15	16	17	18	19	20	21	22	23	24	25	26	27	28	29	30	31	32	33	34	35	36						
WP5A	Trusted research environment blueprint - Establishing a baseline and roadmap			D13.1 5A.1							D13.2 5A.4	D13.3 5A.2																															
WP5B	Trusted research environment blueprint - Development and validation															D14.1 5B.1																											
WP5C	Trusted research environment blueprint - Demonstrating impact & building the network																																										

13.1	Draft Roadmap for EOSC-ENTRUST Blueprint
13.2	Training package for EOSC-ENTRUST Year one Blueprint & Interoperability Framework
13.3	Machine-readable First Edition of the EOSC-ENTRUST TRE Provider Catalogue
13.4	Year one version of EOSC-ENTRUST Blueprint & Interoperability Framework

14.1	Updated Roadmap for EOSC-ENTRUST Blueprint
14.2	Machine-readable Second Edition of the EOSC-ENTRUST TRE Provider Catalogue
14.3	Year two version of EOSC-ENTRUST Blueprint & Interoperability Framework
14.4	Training package for EOSC-ENTRUST Year two Blueprint & Interoperability Framework

15.1	Final Roadmap for EOSC-ENTRUST Blueprint
15.2	EOSC-ENTRUST TRE Service provider catalogue
15.3	Year three version of EOSC-ENTRUST Blueprint & Interoperability Framework
15.4	Training package for EOSC-ENTRUST Year three Blueprint & Interoperability Framework

5A Establishing a baseline and roadmap

M3 Draft Roadmap for EOSC- ENTRUST Blueprint

M9 Machine-readable First Edition of the EOSC- ENTRUST TRE Provider Catalogue

M9 Year one version of EOSC- ENTRUST Blueprint & Interoperability Framework

M9 Training package for EOSC-ENTRUST Year one Blueprint & Interoperability Framework

5B Development and validation

M15 Updated Roadmap for EOSC-ENTRUST Blueprint

M18 Machine-readable Second Edition of the EOSC- ENTRUST TRE Provider Catalogue

M21 Year two version of EOSC-ENTRUST Blueprint & Interoperability Framework

M21 Training package for EOSC-ENTRUST Year two Blueprint & Interoperability Framework

5C Demonstrating impact & building the network

M27 Final Roadmap for EOSC-ENTRUST Blueprint

M30 EOSC-ENTRUST TRE Service provider catalogue

M33 Year three version of EOSC-ENTRUST Blueprint & Interoperability Framework

M33 Training package for EOSC-ENTRUST Year three Blueprint & Interoperability Framework

Effort overview

	WP13 5A	WP14 5B	WP15 5C
CSC-TIETEEN TIETOTEKNIIKAN KESKUS OY	9.0	9.0	9.0
BARCELONA SUPERCOMPUTING CENTRE	1.0	1.0	1.0
MASARYK UNIVERSITY	1.0	1.0	1.0
HEALTH DATA RESEARCH UK	3.0	3.0	3.0
UNIVERSITY OF DUNDEE	1.0	1.0	1.0
UNIVERSITY OF BERGEN SAFE - UiB TSD - UiO HUNTCloud - NTNU	9.0	9.0	9.0
SURF BV	5.0	5.0	5.0
THL - TERVEYDEN JA HYVINVOINNIN LAITOS	1.0	1.0	1.0
Total	31.0	31.0	31.0

Links with other WPs

- **Link to WP3 (Drivers):** Requirements for the blueprint will be gathered from the Driver's forum
- **Link to WP4 (Providers):** Architectures of existing TRE services (Providers) will provide basis for the interoperable network of TRE services in Europe
- **Link to WP6 (Trusted researcher identities and data authorisation):** Core architectural specification activity (WP5) directly linked to technology development activity (WP6)

Planning Months 1-6

- **General Organisation:** Bi-weekly WP5 meetings
- **Due May 2024**
 - **D13.1** - *Draft Roadmap for EOSC-ENTRUST Blueprint*
 - Focused meeting **24.04-25.04** addressing **D13.1**
- **Due November 2024**
 - **D13.2** - *Training package for EOSC-ENTRUST Year one Blueprint & Interoperability Framework*
 - **D13.3** - *Machine-readable First Edition of the EOSC-ENTRUST TRE Provider Catalogue*
 - **D13.4** - *Year one version of EOSC-ENTRUST Blueprint & Interoperability Framework*

WP6abc Trusted researcher identities & data authorisation

Leads: MU

Partners: CSC, GRNET, HEALTH-RI, UiB

General objective: Create a full “AAAI for TREs” solution

- Start with existing solutions (LS AAI), add strong identity vetting, federated authorization and accounting and auditing,
- Through a pilot implementation and feedback gathering to the full production level AAAI for TREs implementation

Results: AAAI for TREs Blueprint and Implementation

WP6a (year 1) Establishing a common terminology and approach

Objectives:

- Establish higher trust in the authentication and authorization in the TREs context
- High quality identity vetting
- Authorization and authorization delegation in distributed federated environments
- 3rd A – Accounting and auditing the access to sensitive objects

Deliverable:

- D6A.1 AAI for TREs Blueprint, 1st version (M12)

WP6b (year 2) Deployment

Objectives:

- Pilot (but with all features) implementation of the AAI for TREs
 - Support for Validators
- Integration of tools and components, increasing TRLs where necessary
- Feedback gathering

Deliverables:

- D6B.1 Training material for the use of AAI for TREs pilot implementation (M18)
- D6B.2 AAI for TREs Blueprint, second version (M24)

WP6c (year 3) Demonstrating impact

Objectives:

- Evolution of the AAI, up to a production level solution
- Extend and adapt the pilot implementation from year 2 (WP6b) to reflect the Blueprint version 2
- Support for Validators

Deliverable:

- D6C.1 AAI for TREs Blueprint, final version (M36)

Links with other WPs

- **Link to WP3 (Drivers):** Requirements for the blueprint will be gathered from the Driver's forum
- **Link to WP4 (Providers):** Architectures of existing TRE services (Providers) will be used to adjust AAAI for TREs solution accordingly
- **Link to WP5 (Trusted research environment blueprint):** Ensure the AAAI for TREs blueprint and its implementation fully fits in the Core architectural specification activity (WP5)
- **Link to WP7 (RO-Crate and workflow processing):** Safe projects and Safe people from the Five Safe; federated authorization and work with secrets in WP7

WP6abc – Tasks

Ta1 The AAI for TREs Blueprint (CSC)

Ta2 Authentication (MU)

Ta3 Authorization (MU)

Ta4 Auditing (GRNET)

Tb1 Pilot deployment of the AAI for TREs (MU)

Tb2 Technology support (CSC)

Tb3 Feedback gathering, modified and new features (GRNET)

Tc1 AAI for TREs Blueprint (MU)

Tc2 Operations (MU)

Effort overview

	WP16 6A	WP17 6B	WP18 6C
MASARYK UNIVERSITY	10.0	10.0	10.0
CSC-TIETEEN TIETOTEKNIIKAN KESKUS OY	2.0	2.0	2.0
MASARYK UNIVERSITY	1.0	1.0	1.0
GRNET	1.0	1.0	1.0
UNIVERSITY OF BERGEN	1.0	1.0	1.0
Total	16.0	16.0	16.0

WP6: Planning Months 1-6

Organization:

- Bi-weekly meetings of Task leaders
- Monthly meeting of the whole WP6

Nothing formal due in the first 6 Months

- Setting work in the Tasks

The first deliverable on M12 (February 2025)

WP7abc RO-Crate and workflow processing

Leads: BSC & UNOTT

Participants: UNIMAN

Objective

Propose mechanisms to safely deploy (or vet) tools and analyses across multiple TREs

Workflows

+

Five Safes
RO-Crates

⇒

WfExS, WES, ...

WP7abc RO-Crate and workflow processing

Task and deliverables

- **WP7a (WP19)**
 - Task 1 Use-cases for the deployment of Five Safes RO-Crate
 - Task 2 Workflow engine processing a Five Safes RO-Crate
- **WP7b (WP20)**
 - Task 1 Verifiable Five Safes RO-Crate
 - Task 2 Handling data security and data curation with workflow orchestrator
- **WP7c (WP21)**
 - Task 1 Wrapping federated analytics within a Five Safes RO-Crate
 - Task 2 Developing a technical blueprint for federated analytics implementation

WP7abc RO-Crate and workflow processing

Tasks and deliverables

WP7abc RO-Crate and workflow processing

RO-Crate profiles mini-primer

- **RO-Crate:** FAIR packaging of data+metadata
 - **Workflow RO-Crate:** .. that describes a *workflow* (e.g. WorkflowHub)
 - **Workflow Run Crate:** ... with *provenance* of workflow execution
 - **Five Safe Crate:** ... who requested, on which TRE, how was it *reviewed/controlled*

Bringing Open Science practices to Trusted Research Environments

WP7abc RO-Crate and workflow processing

TRE-FX

Never trust, always validate

WP7abc RO-Crate and workflow processing

Task 7[abc].1

- Use-cases for deployment of Five Safes RO-Crate
 - Deploy HDR UK Federated Analytics implementation for multiple TREs
 - Evaluate acceptability for Five Safes RO-Crate – evolve profile
 - Validation and implementations

Goal:

- Five Safes RO-Crate can *traverse across TREs* for interoperable workflow execution
- Support and document *Five Safes* process across TREs

WP7abc RO-Crate and workflow processing

Workflow Execution Service backend

- WfExS is a high level workflow orchestrator
 - Delegates on the different engines (cwltool, Nextflow)
- Supports RO-crate in its life cycle
 - Consumes and produces RO-crates
 - Fetches workflows from several sources.
- Encrypted and ephemeral working directory preparation
- Decoupling internet dependent phases
- Remote execution using TES API (coming)

WP7abc RO-Crate and workflow processing

Task 7a.2

- **Goal:** Demonstrate processing five-safes RO-crates

Planning M1-6

- WP internal planning and organization
 - Establishment of periodic meetings
- Initial deployment of Five Safes RO-Crates in a TRE (HDR)
 - Analysis of requirements
 - Reference implementation integration (WfExS)
- Deployable demonstrator based on WfExS
 - 1st release fully supporting RO-crates
 - Testing and validation in a TRE service

Links with other WPs

- WP5 → Feedback to EOSC- ENTRUST Blueprint & Interoperability Framework, RO-Crate
- WP6 → Alignment with AAAI, Safe People, Safe Projects
- WP2 → Training workshops: Requirements and Capabilities Workshop

WP7abc RO-Crate and workflow processing

Workflow Execution Service backend

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Analysis life-cycle using WfExS orchestrator

(dashed lines represent ongoing or future work)

WP7abc RO-Crate and workflow processing

Deliverables & Milestones

D19.1	D7A.1	7A.1 - Deployable Demonstrator of Digital Objects & Workflows Developments	WP7 / WP7A	BSC	DEM	PU	M09
D20.1	D7B.1	7B.1 - Deployable Demonstrator of Digital Objects & Workflows Developments, Second Version	WP14 / WP7B	BSC	DEM	PU	M21
D20.2	D7B.2	7B.2 - Training package for Digital Objects & Workflows	WP14 / WP7B	BSC	DEM	PU	M21
D21.1	D7C.1	7C.1 - Deployable Demonstrator of Digital Objects & Workflows Developments, Final Version	WP21 / WP7C	BSC	DEM	PU	M33
D21.2	D7C.2	7C.2 - Training package for Digital Objects & Workflow	WP21 / WP7C	UNOTT	DEM	PU	M30
D21.3	D7C.3	7C.3 - Peer-reviewed publication describing the lesson learned on the use of RO-Crate within TREs	WP21 / WP7C	BSC	R	PU	M36

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Research Environments

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EOSC-ENTRUST Kick Off Meeting

18 & 19 March 2024

WP7-8-9 Drivers: Validating blueprints across governance domains

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WP7-8-9 Drivers – validating blueprints

(former WP3a-3b-3c)

- Four drivers prototypic for federated, multinational use of TREs for shared analysis of sensitive data
- Provide requirements for the technical workpackages
- Across science domains
- Each driver highlights a specific challenge:
 1. Federated Human Genomics (EMBL, CRG, BSC, CSC)
 2. Social sciences (CESSDA, GESIS, UKDS, TARKI)
 3. Clinical research data (ECRIN, UiO, HDR UK, UNIVDUN)
 4. Health & environmental data in PPP (Turku, CSC, Sigma2)

Drivers – general objectives

Objectives are evolving over time (yr1-3) from requirement definition to demonstrators:

- Inform the EOSC-ENTRUST blueprint and technology development
- Validate the prototypic architecture blueprint against actual TRE solutions
- Determine gaps in the TRE solutions that should be resolved in the TRE blueprint
- Demonstrate the breadth and the depth of the EOSC-ENTRUST architecture

Structure of WP7-9

Effort overview (in PM)

Partner	Role	WP7	WP8	WP9
ELIXIR/EMBL	Dr1 : genomics	2	2	2
CSC	Dr4: PPP	1.5	1.5	1.5
BSC	Dr1: genomics	1	1	1
Health-RI	WP lead	7	7	7
HDRUK	Dr3 clinical	1	0.5	0.5
UNIVDUN	Dr3 clinical	1	0,5	0.5
SIGMA2	Dr4 PPP	1	1	1
UiO	Dr3 clinical	2	1	1
Turku	Dr4 PPP	3	3	4
ECRIN	Dr3 clinical	3.5	3	3.5
CESSDA	Dr2 social sciences	1	1	0.5
TARKI	Dr2 social sciences	1	1.5	1
USSEX	Dr2 social sciences	2	2	1
GESIS	Dr2 social sciences	2.5	2	2

Side note – how do we relate to the EHDS?

EHDS regulation foresees a specific technical infrastructure

Secure Processing Environment (SPE - EHDS) ~ Trusted Research Environment (TRE – EOSC)

Driver 1: Federated Human Genomics

Facilitate (F)EGA data accessibility across TRE network

- EGA development resulted in a huge and rich health data archive but with strict access procedures
- Heterogeneous legislation results in a mixed standard for a partner to be considered 'trusted'
- Technology and use-case diversity implies complex solution reaching goals

Federated
European
Genome-phenome
Archive

Driver 1: Federated Human Genomics

Facilitate (F)EGA data accessibility across TRE network

- Spanish node to provide a joint access node between key European project GDI & platform EGA
- Beacon & Beacon Network to provide trusted discoverability
- Data and metadata accessibility compliant with five-safes framework
- AAAI use case joint effort with WP6

Federated
European
Genome-phenome
Archive

Driver 2: Common standards to enable trans-national sharing of administrative/register and social science data

The Goal –

- Greater interoperability in social science resources
- Allowing collaborative projects at an international scale and at cross-domain level
- Easier access for researchers to sensitive data held in Trusted Research Environments

Driver 2: Common standards - The Challenge

- Some progress already with key transnational projects
- Developed a framework for implementing trans-national data sharing & remote access connections
- Common terminology is needed
- Legislative & governance challenges

**International Secure Data Facility
Professionals Network (ISDFPN)**

Driver 2: Common standards - The Approach

- Use our combine expertise to inform specifications (legal, operational & technical) and to identify & promote common standards
- Aim –
 1. To expand & test this framework with a new secure data service
 2. To explore how this could expand to cross-domain data sharing & the sharing of novel data forms (DVD, quali)
 3. To expand the International Secure Data Facility Professionals Network

Driver 3: Clinical Trials - The Challenge

Journal editors, research funders, industry...

Springer Nature whitepaper on challenges for data sharing in medical field

The NEW ENGLAND JOURNAL of MEDICINE

EDITORIALS

Sharing Clinical Trial Data — A Proposal from the International Committee of Medical Journal Editors

The International Committee of Medical Journal Editors (ICMJE) believes that clinical trial data are used. By changing the requirements for clinical trial data, the ICMJE proposes to ensure that clinical trial data are available to researchers and the public. The ICMJE defines a research project that prospective or a group of people to study the cause-and-effect relationship between a health-related intervention and an outcome. Further details are available at www.icmje.org.

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The NEW ENGLAND JOURNAL of MEDICINE

SOUNDING BOARD

Data Sharing from Clinical Trials — A Research Funder's Perspective

Robert Kiley, Tony Peatfield, Jennifer Hansen, and Fiona Reddington

The Wellcome Trust, Cancer Research UK, and the Gates Foundation are committed to maximizing the value of clinical trial data by ensuring that the trials can be accessed, validated, and ultimately delivered to researchers. The sharing of clinical trial data in 2014 helped researchers identify the final few cases of Ebola virus disease control.¹ And the Journal to encourage the Systolic Blood Pressure Intervention Trial (SPRINT) demonstrates how data to be re-analyzed and uncover

Principles for Responsible Clinical Trial Data Sharing
Our Commitment to Patients and Researchers

Biopharmaceutical companies are committed to enhancing public health through responsible sharing of clinical trial data in a manner that is consistent with the following Principles:

- Safeguarding the privacy of patients
- Respecting the integrity of national regulatory systems
- Maintaining incentives for investment in biomedical research

Figure 11: Problems in sharing data in the medical sciences (n=2,683)

Whitepaper: Practical challenges for researchers in data sharing; 2018. @springernature

Currently only ~10-15% of clinical trials claim to be open to data sharing...

Driver 3: Clinical Trials - The Approach

1

Providers

- IPD Datasets
- Protocols
- Analysis Plans
- Result Summaries
- Published papers
- Data Collection forms
- Consent forms

ecrin

UiO
University of Oslo

Secondary Users

Access

Mix of open and controlled, may be in-situ only

Providers can stipulate exact access arrangements to be applied, including pre-requisites for access

3

ELSI requirements

Governance requirements

Operational requirements

Technical requirements

Security requirements

Community feedback

TRE Providers Forum

2

HDRUK
Health Data Research UK

University of Dundee

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Driver 3: Clinical Trials - The goals

Healthcare data & clinical trials

- Enabling pragmatic trials that aim to evaluate the effectiveness of interventions in real-life routine practice conditions.
- Developing predictive models and increasing knowledge about diagnosis, treatment and outcome.
- Supporting systematic/scoping reviews and development of policy measures by combining different data types.

2

Driver 4: Public-Private interactions between TRE in health and environmental data

- Aims is to demonstrate the opportunities TREs provide to advance research collaboration between public and private organisations
- Gathering and analysing requirements to enable joint processing of sensitive data between research institutions and their partners from the private sector
- Existing sensitive data services will be tested against identified requirements
- Wider research community is engaged to validate the results to demonstrate their applicability to different types of research institutions and SMEs

Driver 4: Use case

- Health Tech Research Group of Turku University of Applied Sciences has long standing collaboration with Eerikkilä Sport & Outdoor Resort.
- Eerikkilä is willing to share their dataset on sport performances and fitness tests for research purposes.
- It has been a challenge to find appropriate solutions for this.
- Existing sensitive data services offered by CSC will be tested and modified to match requirements of public-private interaction. Synthetic data produced by Health Tech is used for testing purposes.

Discussion requirements MVP

GROUP DISCUSSION

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WP10-11-12 TRE Provider Forum

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WP10-11-12 TRE Provider Forum

In this presentation

- Objectives
- Tasks
- Deliverables & Milestones
- Effort overview
- Links with other WPs
- Planning M1-6
- Examples of providers and TREs
- For discussion: how to ensure success and sustainability of the Provider Forum?

European Network of TREs with diverse capabilities.

- TRE Providers Forum consolidate existing expertise and good practices for the common interoperability blueprint.

Objectives

- WP10/4A - TRE Provider Forum - Mapping Baseline Capabilities (M1-M12)
 - **Establish and organise the work of the TRE Provider Forum**
 - **Create the initial TRE inventory**
 - **Collect initial set of requirements for the blueprint**
- WP11/4B - TRE Provider Forum - Validation & Early Adoption (M13-M24)
 - **Facilitate the adoption of blueprint and developed technologies**
 - **Plan overall approach for making TREs part of the EOSC offering**
 - **Support the providers to onboard TREs to the EOSC Portal**
- WP12/4C - TRE Provider Forum - Demonstrating Impact (M25-M36)
 - **Expanding the number of TREs in EOSC**
 - **Reporting findings in adoption of the EOSC-ENTRUST developments**
 - **Agreeing on a sustainability model for the Provider Forum**

Tasks

- M1-M12
 - **T4.1 TRE inventory and requirements (Lead: CSC/EUDAT)**
 - **T4.2 TRE state-of-the art capability mapping and gap analysis (Lead: Sigma2)**
- M13-M24
 - **T4.3 Update requirements management, adoption and evaluation (Lead: BSC)**
 - **T4.4 Building TRE capabilities for EOSC (Lead: CSC/EUDAT)**
- M24-M36
 - **T4.5 Requirement update and capability building for EOSC (Lead: CSC/EUDAT)**
 - **T4.6 Assessing adoption level of the TRE blueprint (Lead: DeIC)**
 - **T4.7 Sustainability model for the TRE Provider Forum (Lead: Sigma2)**

Deliverables

- **Overview: three reports, each one due at the end of the project year**
- Due M12
 - D10.1/4A.1 Provider adoption and evaluation report of Year 1 blueprint and technology, including barriers to adoption & TRE gap analysis
- Due M24
 - D11.1/4B.1 Provider adoption and evaluation report of Year 2 blueprint and technology, including barriers to adoption & EOSC readiness of the TRE providers with recommendations
- Due M30
 - D12.1/4C.1 Final report on adoption and sustainability including EOSC & national perspectives

Milestones

- **Overview: online TRE provider capability inventory by M6, available externally as of M18 (?), two updates**
- Due M6
 - 10/M4A.2 Inventory & summary of current TRE Provider capabilities
 - Means of verification: inventory available online for project participants
- Due M18
 - 11/M4B.1 Inventory & summary of updated TRE Provider capabilities
 - Means of verification: updated inventory available online
- Due 30
 - 12/M4C.1 Inventory & summary of updated TRE Provider capabilities
 - Means of verification: updated inventory available online

	WP10 (total: 33)	WP11 (total: 33)	WP12 (total:33)
CSC (EUDAT), WP lead	6 (task lead)	6 (task lead)	6 (task lead)
BSC	2	2 (task lead)	2
HEALTH-RI	2	2	2
SIGMA2	2 (task lead)	2	2 (task lead)
DeIC	2	2	2 (task lead)
BIP4DAB	2	2	2
UTARTU	2	2	2
PNED	2	2	2
UL	2	2	2
IT4I@VSB	2	2	2
VIB	1	1	1
Sciensano	1	1	1
THL	1	1	1
GRNET	2	2	2
UNIBI	2	2	2
UU	2	2	2

Effort Overview

Links with other WP's 1/2

- **Link to WP13-14-15 (Blueprint):**
 - **Overview: similar information gathering activity needs regarding landscape, need to collaborate on requirements management, feedback loop on TRE blueprint, workshops used for reporting progress and dialogue with Drivers**
 - First version of TRE inventory, initial high-level requirements, and best practices (T4.1) presented in first Requirements and Capabilities workshop (M5A.1)
 - T5A.1 will conduct a survey and interviews among provider forum TRE's > makes sense to align activities with T4.1 and T4.2
 - T4.2 will develop a requirements management framework, while T5A.2 gathers the requirements > to collaborate closely
 - List of reference architectures, requirements mgmt framework, and gap analysis on existing services (T4.2) to be presented in first Evaluation and Adoption workshop (M5A.2)
 - WP11 will compile WP10 and WP13 results into updated requirements list, also give feedback on blueprint
 - T4.5 will perform final requirements update for blueprint, presented at final Requirements and Capabilities workshop
 - T4.6 will review the adoption of outputs from Blueprint and Technical WP's, and report at final Evaluation and Adoption Workshop
 - T4.7 will present the sustainability model at final Evaluation and Adoption Workshop
 - Service catalog (T5C.2) which will include all Provider Forum TRE's, based on information from Provider adoption and evaluation report of Year 2 (D4B.1)

Links with other WP's 2/2

- **Link to WP1-2-3 (Project coordination)**
 - T1.2 will organise info meetings every three months on EOSC, EHDS, and other Data Spaces, meetings will be opened for TRE provider forum members in order to recognise relevant initiatives and projects
 - T1.3 about sustainability of project results > T4.7 about sustainability moden for Provider Forum
- **Link to WP4-5-6 (Communication)**
 - T2C.2 will collect input for summary brochure on EOSC-ENTRUST outputs from providers, provider organizations key stakeholders for dissemination
- **Link to WP7-8-9 (Drivers)**
 - Bi-annual workshops organized by WP13-14-15 require engagement from both Driver and Provider forums

Planning M1-6

- Regular meetings to be established at WP level
 - First meeting was held on 7 March
 - Scheduling poll for next meeting open:
<https://evento.renater.fr/survey/eosc-entrust-wp-providers-meeting-2-24-langzb3d>
- Tasks 4.1 and 4.2 start organizing their work as soon as possible after KOM

T4.1 TRE inventory and requirements (Lead: CSC/EUDAT)

- Create a first version of the inventory of TREs operated by the Forum members.
- Collect an initial set of high-level requirements and best practices on TREs from the Provider Forum members.
 - Align effort with T5A.1 TRE services capabilities baseline analysis for the blueprint which will conduct provider survey and interviews
- The results are presented at the **first Requirements and Capabilities Workshop**

T4.2 TRE state-of the art capability mapping and gap analysis (Lead: Sigma2)

- Perform a more detailed capability mapping of the TREs enhancing the inventory of TREs. Capability mapping includes a listing of used reference architectures.
- Establish a requirements management framework and identify gaps in the existing services. Taking into account:
 - User mobility
 - Tools and workflow mobility
 - Data mobility
- The outcomes are delivered as input for the blueprint architecture and discussed in the **first Evaluation and Adoption Workshop**.
 - Showcase the development of the blueprint & technologies

T4.2 Previous/ongoing efforts: EOSC-Nordic: User Portability

T4.2 Previous/ongoing efforts: NeIC Tryggve & DICE: Tools and Workflow Portability

T4.2 Previous/ongoing efforts: NeIC Tryggve: Data Mobility

<https://sftpbeamer.cbs.dtu.dk/sftp/list?path=/p11&source=host2>

T4.2 Previous/ongoing efforts: DICE, EOSC-Hub (EUDAT)

Implementation on TSD infrastructure

1. Data owner registers a dataset in B2SHARE: Creates a B2SHARE record with a UUID. The Authorization service gets hold of the dataset-UUID association.
2. Data requester requests access to the dataset: Submit a data access request to the authorization service through B2SHARE web interface. The authorization service then notify the data owner about the request.
3. Data owner grants/denies access to the dataset: Through the authorization service.

Secure B2SHARE at CSC

Figure 4: Secure B2SHARE implementation on CSC's sensitive data infrastructure.

Tryggve ELSI “Checklist”

- ELSI issues & GDPR compliance
 - Ethical reviews & Informed consents
 - Controllers
 - Legal basis
 - Data processing agreements
 - Data Protection Impact Assessments
 - Data sharing
 - Other legal considerations

Tryggve Checklist on ELSI issues and GDPR compliance

Cohorts / Datasets	
List and number the cohorts/datasets that will be used in the project	
1. 2. 3. 4. 5.	
Ethical reviews and informed consents	
Has the project (or parts of the project) undergone ethical review?	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Yes, parts <input type="checkbox"/> No <input type="checkbox"/> Needs to be confirmed
● What are the <i>limitations of use</i> in the ethics approval, if any? List per cohort/dataset <ul style="list-style-type: none">○ e.g. only for research on certain types of diseases, sharing only within certain geographical boundaries, etc	
1. 2. 3. 4. 5.	
Have informed consents been collected from the research subjects?	<input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> Yes, for some cohorts <input type="checkbox"/> No <input type="checkbox"/> Needs to be confirmed
● What are the <i>limitations of use</i> defined in the informed consent, if any? List per cohort/dataset <ul style="list-style-type: none">○ e.g. only for research on certain types of diseases, sharing only within certain geographical boundaries etc	

T4.7 Sustainability model for the TRE Provider Forum, (Lead: Sigma2)

- Discuss options for continuing the activity of TRE Provider Forum beyond the duration of the project
- Suggest a model for sustained activity in alignment with EOSC. The model will include onboarding strategies for new TRE providers and for new adoption cases.
- The outcome will be presented for comments in the **final Evaluation and Adoption Workshop**.

TRE Provider Organizations

- BSC
- IT Centre for Science CSC
- Danish e-Infrastructure Consortium (DeiC)
- PNED GIE (ELIXIR-LU)
- BIP4DAB
- ELIXIR-SI
- GRNET
- HIC
- IT4I@VSB
- UU (NBIS/ELIXIR-SE)
- Sigma2 AS
- Health-RI
- U Tartu
- UNIBI/de.NBI/ELIXIR-DE
- Sciansano/VIB

Name of organization

Name and country of TRE

Type of TRE and maturity level

- *Describe the maturity briefly (sentence or two) in your own words as you wish*

Main use cases

IT Centre for Science CSC

Name and country of TRE: Finland, Sensitive Data Desktop

URL: <https://research.csc.fi/-/sd-desktop>

Type of TRE and maturity level

- In production since 2022
- SD Desktop provides an isolated, secure private cloud computing environment accessible via a web user interface. All data processing takes place in Finland.
- Restricted version of SD Desktop is accredited for secondary use of health and social data by the Finnish register data authority Findata

Main use cases

For all types of academic research, also RDI research in public-private collaboration as long as research results made public

National e-Infrastructure Services (Sigma2 AS)

- Norway

Local university level

- TSD - UiO
TRL: 9. Multipurpose.
- HUNT Cloud - NTNU
TRL: 9. Multipurpose.
- SAFE - UiB
TRL: 9. Multipurpose.

TSD (Services for Sensitive Data)

University: University of Oslo (UiO)

Service URL: <https://www.uio.no/english/services/it/research/sensitive-data/>

Type of TRE and maturity level

- *SPE: Secure Processing Environment. Main Features:*
 - *secure processing environments that integrate with custom data collections tools for web and smartphones (Nettskjema), research participant consents services and high-performance computing (HPC).*
 - *The technological configuration consists of VMware, a HPC system (3,200 CPU), an Enterprise Storage System (10PE) and tape backup.*
 - *Parts of the HPC capacity and storage is provided through the TSD-Sigma2 collaboration.*
- *Technology Readiness Level: TRL9*

Use cases

- serves the largest number of end-users (N~10,000) from a wide-range of scientific fields (N~2,000 projects)

SAFE (Secure Access to Research Data and E-infrastructure)

University: University of Bergen (UiB)

Service URL: <https://www.uib.no/safe>

Type of TRE and maturity level

- *SPE: Secure Processing Environment. Main Features:*
 - *The infrastructure is based on virtual Windows- and Linux servers that integrate with a wide range of scientific software according to the user's needs, including secure video recordings, automatic speech transcription and REDCap for data collection.*
- *Technology Readiness Level: TRL9*

Use cases

- SAFE serves ~1,800 end-users in ~500 projects and hosts more than 1PE of data, from humanities, social sciences, law, economics, psychology, art and health

HUNT Cloud

University: Norwegian University of Science and Technology (NTNU)

Service URL: <https://www.ntnu.edu/mh/huntcloud>

Type of TRE and maturity level

- *SPE: Secure Processing Environment. Main Features:*
 - *The technological configuration consists of OpenStack cloud orchestration (~3000 CPU) and Ceph software defined storage (~10PE raw disk) and 40 GPU accelerators.*
 - *HUNT Cloud holds third-party verified ISO certificates for quality management (ISO/IEC 9001), information security management (ISO/IEC 27001), and privacy management (ISO/IEC 27701 from 2024).*
- *Technology Readiness Level: TRL9*

Use cases

- HUNT Cloud provides Linux-based secure processing environments that are utilized by ~300 researchers in ~100 projects

Danish e-Infrastructure Consortium (DeiC)*

Academics/local university level

- Computerome
TRL: 9. HPC. Life science research. (CPH-U, DTU, DeiC)
- UCloud
TRL: 9. HPC. Multipurpose. ISO27001-certified. (SDU, DTU, AAU, AU, DeiC)

Public/national level

- 2 x Forskermaskinen (“The researcher-machine”).
Statistics Denmark (DST): TRL: 9. Powerful virtual-machine environment. Socio-economic/humanities projects.
The Danish Health Data Authority (SDS): TRL: 9. Powerful virtual-machine environment. Health-studies and quality development projects.
- API for transferring data to national HPC facilities in progress, supervised by DeiC (and KOR).
- Danish Genome Center (NGC)
TLR: 9. HPC (connected to Forskermaskinen). Genome sequencing and personal medicine.
- *National vision/strategy*
TLR: 2. One access-point to all Danish health data and analysis capabilities (technology concept formulated: Hub’n’Spokes-model - in early stages of planning).

Potentially others – national survey in planning stage.

**DeiC is not currently a direct provider but involved in multiple collaborations.*

IT4I supercomputing and data services

University: IT4Innovations, VSB-Technical University of Ostrava, Czech Rep., <https://www.it4i.eu>

Type of TRE and maturity level

- **National provider of supercomputing services** as part of e-infrastructure of the Czech Republic <https://e-infra.cz>
- **Karolina supercomputer** (EuroHPC JU petascale system since 2021) – 106,752 CPU cores, 576 Nvidia A100 GPUs, 4,608 CPU cores cloud service (OpenStack) <https://www.it4i.cz/en/infrastructure/karolina>
- Member of LUMI supercomputer consortium (currently #1 in Europe and #5 in Top500) <https://www.lumi-supercomputer.eu>
- **Project data storage – 18PB** incl. S3 object storage
- ISO 270001 certified Information Security Management System in provisioning of supercomputing infrastructure services, solution of computationally intensive problems, performance of advanced data analysis and simulations, and processing of large data sets since 2018
- **Technology Readiness Level: TRL9**

Main use cases

- **Supercomputing services** (incl. data services related to SC) to academia and research institutes, partially to industry and public institutions, 80% open access grant competition, ~2000 active users (in 2023), incl. 54 commercial users, 292 EuroHPC users.
 - Scientific domains include Material science, bioinformatics, engineering, physics, computer science inc. artificial intelligence, ...
 - Industrial use in engineering, biomedicine, hydrology, artificial intelligence and data processing,
- **LEXIS v2 platform** – Easy and secure access to HPC, cloud and data services incl. workflows management and resource orchestration, <https://docs.lexis.tech>
- **European Digital Innovation Hub** (EDIH Ostrava) – provisioning of computing and data resources (Test before invest), and expertise to SMEs incl. training, <https://edihostrava.cz/en/>

How to Ensure Sustainability of Provider Forum?

- How can we provide value for original members?
- How can we attract, engage, and successfully on-board new members?
- How do we make sure that every member is active, and is heard?
- Who should the forum be for: technical experts, RDM experts, legal experts, managers, directors...?
- What risks should we be aware of and steer clear from when establishing the forum?

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EOSC ENTRUST Kick-off Meeting

The Horizon Europe EOSC Partnership

Ute Gunsenheimer, Secretary General, EOSC Association

Funded by
the European Union

April 19, March 2024

Today's Topics

- The EOSC Association
- The Horizon Europe co-programmed EOSC Partnership
- The INFRAEOSC Project Collaboration

Purpose & Benefits

The EOSC Association

The Voice of the Community

The Purpose of the EOSC Association

Incorporation, 29 July 2020

- (1) to provide a single voice for the advocacy and representation of the broader EOSC stakeholder community;
- (2) to promote the alignment of European Union research policy and priorities with activities coordinated by the Association;
- (3) to enable seamless access to data through interoperable services that address the entire research data life cycle.

eosc 162 Members and 88 Observers

A strong memberbase

eosc The Benefits of being a Member

- Actively **shape the strategic development** of the European Open Science Cloud by contributing to the Partnership's [Strategic Research and Innovation Agenda](#) and its [Multi-Annual Roadmaps](#);
- Actively **guide the strategy** for the EOSC implementation phase by contributing to EOSC-A's [Advisory Groups, Task Forces and Working Groups](#);
- **Participate** in General Assembly meetings with voting rights;
- **Gain a voice** in relevant policy dialogues and access to policy makers at the European and national levels;
- **Showcase** the contributions and impact of your organisation;
- **Network** with like-minded people and become an ambassador within your organisation's peer group.

The EOSC Association Brain-Pool

13 Task Forces with over 400 volunteers

Implementation of EOSC

- Rules of Participation compliance monitoring
- PID policy and implementation
- Researcher engagement and adoption

Technical challenges on EOSC

- Technical interoperability of data and services
- Infrastructure for quality research software
- AAI Architecture

Metadata and data quality

- Semantic interoperability
- FAIR metrics and data quality

Research careers and curricula

- Data stewardship curricula and career paths
- Research careers, recognition and credit
- Upskilling countries to engage in EOSC

Sustaining EOSC

- Financial sustainability
- Long-term data preservation

Task Forces / Summary of Achievements

Task Forces in Numbers

Open call for EOSC-A Task Force members

- FAIR Metrics and Digital Objects
- EOSC Technical and Semantic Interoperability
- Long-term Data Retention
- Health Data

21 March – 21 April 2024

Horizon Europe co-programmed EOSC Partnership

Launched June 2021

One billion euros commitment by the European Union and the EOSC Association

Strategic Research and Innovation Agenda

Open Science practices and skills are rewarded and taught, becoming the 'new normal'

Standards, tools and services allow researchers to find, access, reuse and combine results

Sustainable and federated infrastructures enable open sharing of scientific results

Multi-annual roadmap sets priority activities and outcomes grouped by three implementation levels – European, National, Institutional

Three phases of MAR:

1. 2021-2022: development towards a functional federation of infrastructure
2. 2023-2024: expansion to production that generates added value
3. 2025-2027: expansion to develop impact from Open Science

Commitments

The MoU is established between the Partners

The EU represented by the Commission
The EOSC Association (“Partners other than the Union”), including its constituent entities (members)

Governance: Partnership Board

Composition: Representatives appointed by the Partners other than the Union, Commission officials and Representatives of the Steering Board

The MoU is a contractual arrangement, not legally binding

Commitments of the EC

To duly take into account the input and advice from EOSC-A when defining call topics relative to the scope and objectives of the SRIA

Scope & objectives

To contribute to the objectives defined in the SRIA incl. the KPIs to measure progress
Expected financial and in-kind commitments by the partners (490 MEUR + 500 MEUR)

Commitments of EOSC-A

In-kind contributions
Monitoring and Reporting

 Commitments of the European Commission

 Commitments of the EOSC Association

Demonstrating Added Value by 2025 – EOSC-A

Additional Activities of EOSC-A Members

AAR 2022 (Final)
EUR 292.162.962
1607 FTEs
Supporting ecosystem development : 33M EUR

AAP 2023
EUR 383.929.296
2105 FTEs
Supporting ecosystem development: 71M EUR

22-23 May 2023
6th General Assembly

AAP 2024
EUR 335.382.236
2630 FTEs
Supporting ecosystem development: 67M EUR

Commitments

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eosc Delivering EOSC – the Process

The critical role of the INFRAEOSC Projects

EOSC Community

EOSC Community

EUROPEAN OPEN SCIENCE CLOUD

Community

INFRA-EOSC Projects

eosc EOSC-A Members EOSC-A Mandated Organisations EOSC-A Task Forces

Working with the INFRAEOSC Projects

INFRAEOSC Working Groups

Group	Objective, scope, project representatives
HE Communication & Engagement 	<ul style="list-style-type: none">• Enhance collaboration, increase synergies, minimize overlap, and increase visibility of HE EOSC-related project results through coordinated communication and engagement activities• Monthly meetings• Engagement / communication officers
HE Technology 	<ul style="list-style-type: none">• Ensure efficient and coherent development of EOSC by fostering cross-project alignment on technical developments, maximizing the impact of project outputs and ensuring the long-term sustainability of EOSC• Monthly meetings (e.g., discussing architectural and technology issues) & on-site meeting for EOSC Technical Coordinators' Cockpit (ETCC) (with wider audience)• Technical coordinators
HE EOSC Impact 	<ul style="list-style-type: none">• Align with HE EOSC-related projects in achieving their EOSC-related impact, with the aim of comprehensively showcasing the projects' contribution and demonstrating the added value of both the projects and EOSC as a whole• Expert group, meetings on demand• Project representatives involved in the measuring impact of project results

eosc Roadmap

The Macro-Roadmap for the Implementation of EOSC Visualisation accessible via <https://eosc.eu/roadmap>

- Implementation challenges ▼
- Landscape, Monitoring and Engagement ▼
- Skills, training, rewards, recognition ▼
- Supporting grand societal challenges ▼
- Widening to public and private sectors and going global ▼

Winter School 2024

29 January - 1 February 2024 / Thessaloniki, Greece

eosc.eu | [#eoscwinterschool2024](https://twitter.com/eoscwinterschool2024)

Supported by

6 Opportunity Areas

<https://eosc.eu/eosc-focus-project/winter-school-2024/>

Opportunity Areas and Sessions

The EOSC Winter School sessions are organised according to EOSC technical development Opportunity Areas (OAs). Participants will be able to select and follow one parallel session.

Click on your Opportunity Area to see detailed descriptions of the sessions.

OA1: PIDs

OA2: Metadata, Ontologies & Interoperability

OA3: FAIR Assessment & Alignment

OA4: User & Resource Environments

OA5: Skills, Training, Rewards, Recognition & Upskilling

OA6: Open Scholarly Communication

Opportunity Area 1: PIDs

Opportunity Area 2:
Metadata, Ontologies &
Interoperability

Opportunity Area 3:
FAIR Assessment & Alignment

Opportunity Area 4:
User & Resource Environments

Opportunity Area 5:
Skills, Training, Rewards,
Recognition, Upskilling

Opportunity Area 6:
Open Scholarly Communication

eosc

EOSC Symposium 2024

21 - 23 October / Berlin, Germany

eosc.eu | #eoscsymposium2024

In cooperation with

EOSC-SIESTA

Project overview

Álvaro López García (coordinator) aloga@ifca.unican.es
IFCA, CSIC-UC

Funded by
the European Union

SIESTA in a nutshell

- HORIZON-INFRA-2023-EOSC-01-06 call
- 5M€, lump-sum scheme
- Duration: 1st Jan 2024 – 31st Dec 2026
- 13 partners (ES, IT, FR, SK, DK, SE)
 - Academic and Research: CSIC, IISAS, INSERM, ISI, CNRS, ULE, SRU, NRU
 - Law: Javier de la Cueva
 - SMEs & Industry: algoWATT, Cendio, interWAY
 - Statistical offices: INE
- <https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/101131957>

Objectives

Deliver trusted cloud-based environments for the analysis of sensitive data, built in a reproducible way, and a set of services to ease the secure sharing through state-of-the-art anonymization techniques

1. Enhance the EOSC Exchange services with cloud-based trusted environments for the analysis of sensitive data in the EOSC demonstrating the feasibility of the FAIR principles over them
2. Study, explore and demonstrate the feasibility of FAIR management and processing of sensitive data, showcasing the benefits for society, science and research
3. Deliver tools for the secure anonymization or pseudonymisation of datasets, allowing rightholders to safely release sensitive data through the EOSC Exchange
4. Provide rightholders with best practices and methodologies for the release of sensitive data following FAIR principles
5. Extend the service offer and the capabilities being offered through the EOSC portal, coordinating with the operational and management activities carried out by the EOSC partnership and related projects

SIESTA Concept

- **Different access methods based on the data sensitivity:** from collaborative development environments (like JupyterHub) for low risk data, to access through security hardened remote desktop solutions with limited capabilities, strict network controls and VPN access for higher sensitivity levels.
- **Internal repositories** allow the installation of **software components and libraries only from trusted** sources that have been previously approved.
- **User-provided predefined software components that have been endorsed and approved**, allowing the **offload of user workflow tasks into the platform**, accessing sensitive data.
- **Assisted anonymization tools** for data ingestion and **risk-disclosure evaluation tools** for data stage out, allowing the improvement of the privacy levels of the shared data.
- A **tamper-proof** component for keeping track of all **relevant transactions**, providing auditing mechanisms.
- **Integrations with the EOSC Core and Exchange**, allowing for instance the inclusion of existing datasets, the generation and storage of anonymized or synthetic data in EOSC compliant repositories or the delivery of trusted and secure thematic data spaces into the EOSC.

SIESTA Concept

- Provide safe and trusted access to sensitive data
- Following tiered model for data sensitiveness
 0. Fully open data, no need to use a trusted research environment.
 1. Very low risk. Pseudonymised data with very low linking risk. Unlikely to cause harm.
 2. Low risk. Strongly pseudonymised datasets with some indirect identifiers.
 3. Average risk. Pseudonymised personal data and confidential organisations information.
 4. High risk. Weak or no de-identification and very sensitive commercial data.
 5. Very high risk. Very sensitive personal data or highly confidential government or commercial data.
- Initially Focus on categories to 2 to 5+6, with increased level of security, different entry methods, different restrictions
- Infrastructure as Code to ensure reproducibility of the compute environment

Tiered model (data sensitiveness) implications

- Different data sensitiveness (tiered model) coupled with different access models
 - Provide different access levels: e.g. remote interactive sessions (levels 0-2), remote desktop (level 3), remote desktop with limited capabilities (level 4), execution of trusted code or SMPC (level 5)
- Other platform level security implications
 - E.g. SIESTA audit system has high sensitivity
- SIESTA aims to address these security aspects through an Infrastructure as Code
 - Map platform deployments to certified resource providers (SIESTA involves partners whose compute resources are certified with ISO27001:2017 and National Cybersecurity Schemes)

IF(A)

CSIC

CONSEJO SUPERIOR DE INVESTIGACIONES CIENTÍFICAS

ens
Esquema Nacional de
Seguridad

SIESTA implementation and co-design

Five complementary cases:

1. **Epidemiology:** (CSIC, INSERM, ISI) development of an ecosystem with data collected by the SIESTA team from different sources (population, mobility, surveillance, etc.), plus data from collaborative surveillance systems, and with the addition of last generation models able to study propagation patterns of generic infectious diseases.
2. **Medical imaging:** (SRU, NRU, CNRS) development of (neuro)imaging data analysis pipelines integrated with the EOSC platform that allow expert and non-expert users to carry out analyses on public and non-public neuroimaging (fMRI, EEG, MEG) datasets including demographic, health and questionnaire (tabular) data as covariates.
3. **Energy:** (ALWA) secured Renewable Energy Community (REC) information hub, able to guarantee a trusted, privacy-compliant, seamless and even cross-border access, reuse and valorization of technical information associated with energy consumption, production and storage.
4. **Text anonymization on sensitive data:** (ULE) tools that allow anonymizing documents or any information containing text, with special focus on personal data and also on information related to locations, organisations, addresses, emails, finance or any information that could lead to identifying a person or organisation.
5. **Demography:** (CSIC, INE) tools to improve the anonymization of the data to be shared, the creation of designed populations whose data can be shared without privacy concerns and systems to analyse in a reproducible FAIR way the data without the need of a direct access.

High level architecture

EOSC-SIESTA follows the [C4 model](#) and notation for its architecture definition

WP structure

Project organization

Project coordination:

- siesta-po@listas.csic.es

Thank you for your attention

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the European Union

TITAN presentation

Trusted environments for confidenTiAl computiNg and secure data sharing

Antonio Skarmeta UMU

Objectives

Enriching the EOSC with a **software platform solution for confidential data collaboration and secure and privacy-preserving data processing.**

- Objective 1: Collect legal, technical, and architectural requirements and define a platform architecture for secure sharing of sensitive data and publishing anonymised data sets in the EOSC Interoperability Framework IF.
- Objective 2: Develop secure data sharing and auditing mechanisms for sensitive data, including secure data zones, data access control, and end-to-end data protection (storage - transfer - processing).
- Objective 3: Develop an end-to-end secure data processing framework for collaborative and privacy-preserving Machine Learning (ML) using Trusted Execution Environments.
- Objective 4: Implement confidential mechanisms, algorithms, and tools with cloud infrastructure platforms and the EOSC IF, and validate solutions in sensitive data-driven use cases (government and healthcare)
- Objective 5: Disseminate and promote the solutions for data governance and stewardship through collaboration with EOSC Partnership initiatives, standardisation, and integrating with the EOSC infrastructure

Ambition

- TITAN builds on the vision of combining a thorough **understanding of legal and technical aspects** to build solutions for a new paradigm of secure access to sensitive public data and applications and support data-driven science.
- Solutions envisioned in TITAN align by design with the objectives of the **EOSC IF**, aiming to increase the value of scientific data assets through wide-spread availability and reduce the costs of scientific data management while ensuring adequate data protection following EU regulations.
- While realising the challenges of achieving technical, semantic, organisational, and legal interoperability, TITAN will develop automated technical solutions to manage, govern and bridge the gaps in semantic, organisational, and legal interoperability.
- TITAN's solutions will **help practitioners solve their regulatory and compliance challenges**, as well as semantic, and organisational interoperability challenges. To validate the utility of TITANs solutions for the EOSC IF and ensure that results are exploitable.
- The developed solutions will be integrated **with EOSC-compliant data sources** and applications already during the project by **publishing them in the EOSC resource catalogue**.

Vision

New paradigm of secure access to sensitive public data and applications.

- TITAN will focus on end-to-end secure data sharing and collaboration platform requires advancements in network security, **distributed access control**, security domain segmentation, application of state-of-the-art **protection for data in use**, as well as **usable and scalable data anonymisation**
- Three main areas
 - **Domain 1: Confidential data processing enabling confidential collaborative data processing:** memory encryption, confidential computing, remote attestation, confidential GPUs, confidential ML.
 - **Domain 2: Scalable data anonymisation for wide data access:** Differential Privacy, k-anonymity, Secure Multiparty Computation (SMC), Multi-Party Computations (MPC), Zero-Knowledge Proof (ZK-SNARKs), and Homomorphic Secret Sharing (HSS).
 - **Domain 3: Distributed access control and transaction logging using decentralised solutions:** blockchain technologies, network security domains, cloud security zones, access control and management.

- Privacy-preserving, collaborative (confidential multi-party) ML by combining the aforementioned techniques and leveraging Federated ML. To achieve immutability of the learning data model, the model will be stored on the **distributed ledger**.
- Discovery, sharing, and federation of heterogeneous data from multiple sources, **semantic interoperability data models**
- TEEs to implement confidential data processing for the shared datasets
- TITAN will develop an improved **access control management ecosystem** through the application of DLTs, and more concretely smart-contract-enabled blockchains

WP Structure

Integration with Data Space Business Association Architecture

TITAN will develop a scalable and flexible cryptographic mechanisms for data-centric security, beyond the use of well-known and established protocols (e.g. (D)TLS or IPsec).

Use of Identity-Based Encryption (IBE) and CP-ABE were considered as encryption approaches in distributed ledgers

How they can be used as part of data space connectors

eosc | SIESTA Organization

Use cases

- Use Case 1: Confidential sharing and collaboration with sensitive agrifood government data.

- Use Case 2: Collaborative Use of ML in Healthcare

Thank you for your attention

Trusted environments for sensitive data management in EOSC

18 & 19 March 2024

EOSC-ENTRUST Kick Off Meeting

Funded by
the European Union

Trusted environments for sensitive data management in EOSC

1. 9.00-9.15: EOSC partnership - Ute Gunsenheimer
2. 9.15-9.25: SIESTA - Alvaro López
3. 9.25-9.35: TITAN - Antonio Skarmeta
4. 9.35-10.20: Panel discussion moderated by Emily Jefferson

Panel

Emily Jefferson
HDR UK
Moderator

Ute Gunsenheimer
EOSC Association

Alvaro López
SIESTA

Antonio Skarmeta
TITAN

Jonathan Tedds
ELIXIR / EOSC-ENTRUST

Discussion

- What is the added value of a synergy between SIESTA, TITAN and EOSC-ENTRUST?
- What synergies can be identified with other initiatives as GAIA-X and Data Space
- Which technologies are envisioned in the projects to cope with privacy
-

ENTRUST

European Network of Trusted
Research Environments

 www.eosc-entrust.eu

 [@eosc-entrust](https://twitter.com/eosc-entrust)

 [/company/eosc-entrust](https://www.linkedin.com/company/eosc-entrust)

Funded by
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EOSC-ENTRUST Kick Off Meeting

18 & 19 March 2024

EOSC-ENTRUST strategic alignment & outreach

Funded by
the European Union

EOSC-ENTRUST strategic alignment & outreach

1. WP1-2-3 Project coordination and strategic alignment
2. WP4-5-6 Communication, Dissemination & Outreach

10 min presentations: objectives, work plan for next 6 months & connections to other WPs. Discussion.

WP1-2-3 Coordination & alignment

Please provide a 10-min overview of your WP:

- Objectives
- Tasks
- Deliverables & Milestones
- Effort overview
- Links with other WPs
- Planning M1-6

WP1-2-3 Coordination & alignment

Objectives

1. Ensuring EOSC-ENTRUST meets its objectives and work plan with high-quality guidelines
2. Defining and implementation of communication procedures
3. Establish a project governance structure
4. Set up the strategic alignment with the EOSC Partnership and projects, the EHDS, and projects funded under HE/EC calls
5. Investigate potential exploitation as a route to sustainability

WP1-2-3 Coordination & alignment

Tasks

WP1 - Mapping Baseline Capabilities (M12)

- T1.1 Project coordination and quality assurance ([ELIXIR](#))
- T1.2 Strategic alignment and contribution to the EOSC Partnership, EHDS and other relevant initiatives ([EUDAT](#))
- T1.3 Exploitation as a route to sustainability ([ELIXIR](#))

WP2 - Validation and Early Adoption (M24)

- T1B.1 Project coordination, quality assurance and External Advisory Board ([ELIXIR](#))
- T1B.2 Strategic alignment and contribution to the EOSC Partnership and other relevant initiatives ([CSC](#))
- T1B.3 Exploitation and long-term sustainability mapping ([ELIXIR](#))

WP3 - Building the Network (M36)

- T1C.1 Project coordination, quality assurance and External Advisory Board ([ELIXIR](#))
- T1C.2 Strategic alignment and contribution to the EOSC Partnership and other relevant initiatives ([CSC](#))
- T1C.3 Exploitation and long term sustainability plan delivery ([ELIXIR](#))

WP1-2-3 Coordination & alignment

Deliverables & Milestones

	Deliverable	Partner	Due
D1.1	1A.1 Project handbook and Risk Monitoring Framework	ELIXIR	M3
D1.2	1A.2 Project Data Management Plan	ELIXIR	M6
D2.1	1B.1 Project Data Management Plan update	ELIXIR	M21
D3.1	1C.2 Paper on EOSC-ENTRUST International Impact	ELIXIR	M30
D3.2	1C.1 Long term Sustainability Plan	ELIXIR	M33
	Milestone	Partner	Due
1	M1A.1 EOSC-ENTRUST Kick Off Meeting	ELIXIR	M1
2	M1B.1 EOSC-ENTRUST Sustainability Workshop	ELIXIR	M21

WP1-2-3 Coordination & alignment

Links to other WPs

- Communications (WP4-5-6)
 - D2A.1 Dissemination, Communication & Exploitation Plan (M6)
 - T1A.3 Exploitation as a Route to Sustainability (M12)
 - T1B.2 Strategic Alignment and contribution to the EOSC Partnership & other relevant initiatives (M24)
 - T1C.3 Exploitation & Long term Sustainability Plan Delivery (M36)
- All WPs and Partners
 - Monitoring and reporting

WP1-2-3 Coordination & alignment

Planning M1-6

- Mobilise project
 - Facilitate WPs and project boards to kick-start activities
 - Monitoring process and reporting to General Assembly/Advisory Board
 - Provide centralised support and coordination across WPs and activities
- Preparation of D1.1 - Project Handbook and Risk Monitoring Framework
 - Building on PM2 and previous project handbooks (CONVERGE, B1MG, ..)
 - Tailored for lump sum grants
- Preparation of D1.2 - Project Data Management Plan
 - Project data management plan initially focused to the management of the project

Comparing 1+MG and EHDS

1+MG EDIC Federated Secure Processing Environment (SPE)

EHDS

- Data from **all** hospitals / labs / research can be requested
- Data must be **extracted each time** from the **(different) sources**
- In case of **cross-border access**, this happens **in parallel** in the **different countries**
- Available data **not harmonised**
- **Federated computing difficult** without harmonisation; **central SPE** as solution
- **Subject-level data discovery** is **impossible**

1+MG EDIC (authorised participant in EHDS)

- Availability is **limited to data brought into the EDIC**
- Data are available in a **harmonised fashion**
- Data can be **queried "in situ"** and **remain in the country**
- **Subject-level data discovery** is **possible**
- **"Manual"** and **Federated processing** (analytics, AI and ML)

Unique selling points (USPs) of 1+MG

- **By depositing data in 1+MG institutions will be fulfilling EHDS obligations**
- **Single review process** will be **cheaper** and more **efficient** via central DAC
- Possibility to **find relevant patients**
- **Shorter response** times (≥ 1 month) – **quicker reviews**
- Data already **prepared for secondary use** rather than with health data holder
- **Qualified infrastructure platform** to accommodate **genomics data processing**
- Potential to **orchestrate a federated processing** across borders
- **Critical mass** to support **evidence-based healthcare**: Users of 1+MG can tap **immediately** into the **entire EU-wide data collection** in a **single mechanism**
- Operating **based on the trust of people** due to **high transparency** and **consent mechanisms** that include **opt-in/opt-out** and **easy object mechanisms**

More information: <https://framework.onemilliongenomes.eu/gdi-coordination@elixir-europe.org>

GDI project receives funding from the European Union's Digital Europe Programme under grant agreement number 101081813.

Strategic alignment priorities

- EOSC
- Health Data Space
- Other Data Spaces
- Any other relevant sectorial initiative
- ...

Why strategic alignment is important

- 2024 is a critical year for EOSC:
 - The Federation will be piloted with the set up of some nodes
 - The rules of participation will be defined (are these aligned with the EOSC ENTRUST Federation requirements/blueprint? Why and how the EOSC ENTRUST resources should contribute?)
 - The governance of the Federation will be established (will the partners of EOSC ENTRUST have a role?)
 - The tripartite collaboration will identify a governance model for EOSC post 2027
 - It will be clear how EOSC will be sustained and funded (what is the role of the results of EOSC ENTRUST? Does the TRE network has a role in the future?)
- European Parliament and Council negotiators have agreed to establish a European Health Data Space (EHDS) to facilitate access to personal health data and enhance secure data sharing for public interests
 - How does this impact on the TRE providers?
- EOSC is one of the 6 Data Spaces prioritised for the integration with Simpl
 - Does this bring constraints or opportunities?
- More than 14 data spaces are under constructions
 - What are the implications?

To answers all these questions

- We need to clarify what we want to strategically achieve as a project
- We need to understand the landscape by engaging with the key stakeholders
 - DG CNECT, DG RTD, DG SANTE
 - Several partners have key roles in the strategic initiatives (Members of EOOSC-A; INFRAEOOSC project; EHDS related projects and initiatives (EHDS2 pilot; GDI; GoE; EUCAIM); DSSC; etc.)

- We need to influence the landscape
 - SRIA 2.0 consultation
 - EOOSC-A Task Forces
 - EOOSC Technical and Semantic Interoperability
 - Health Data Task Force
 - FAIR metrics and digital objects
 - Long-term Data Retention
 - Governance post-2027 (via EOOSC-A; MSs and ACs)
 -

Examples of strategic alignment activities

- Regular meetings with EOSC and EHDS strategic stakeholders
- Contribution to EOSC consultation (SRIA, Task Forces)
- Coordination meeting organised by EC, 20-21 June, Brussels
- Active contribution to the EOSC-A Health Task Force / Technical & Semantic Interoperability
- EOSC & Data Spaces Symposium
- Liaison with MSs & ACs to influence governance discussions

Alignment with EOSC

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The EOSC Federation and the role of Nodes

Main points in the position paper

<https://eosc.eu/wp-content/uploads/2023/11/20231112-Short-paper-on-the-EOSC-Federation-draft-v3.pdf>

EOSC Federation

- is a federation of distributed systems ('system of systems')
- enables collaboration to achieve common goals and users to access additional resources beyond their usual environment
- has policies and rules defined by the legal entity governing the EOSC Federation
- consists of multiple "Nodes"
- can be scaled by adding more Nodes

EOSC Nodes

- contain resources adding value to the Federation
- act as the legal representative that can interact with EOSC's governance structure
- offer interfaces that comply with the EOSC Interoperability Framework
- control their own operations and resources and ensure that policies are followed within the Node
- may vary in their local policies, the resources to which they provide access and the infrastructure on which they are built

Initiatives (European, national, regional, institutional or thematic) may join the EOSC Federation and become EOSC Nodes when they meet the requirements listed above

Revised draft

Additional feedback received in Dec'23

- Instruct-ERIC
- Uppsala University
- CREAM
- Oslo University
- ERIC-forum
- Athena

Points highlighted

- Clarify what is legal representation of a node
- Define how nodes interact with the EOSC governance
- Explain how RIs map on to nodes and EOSC federation
- Explain the role of the EOSC EU node in the EOSC federation
- Elaborate how nodes will be funded

Latest news

- Regular meetings with EC, EOSC-A Board and EOSC Steering Board to define the decision making process (key milestone: 16 April 2024, European Tripartite event)

Key questions for EOSC ENTRUST

- EOSC ENTRUST is expected to enrich the EOSC Federation with resources (sensitive data, TRE services, etc.)
 - What resources can be “shared”?
 - How?
 - Why?
- Is the EOSC ENTRUST blueprint defining some of the EOSC Federation standards, policies, etc?
- Is EOSC ENTRUST a Node? or is EOSC ENTRUST building a Node? Or are the RIs part of EOSC ENTRUST a node?

EOSC EU Node Value Proposition

- **Facilitate** the creation of the “*Web of FAIR data and interoperable services*” (aka. EOSC Federation) under the Open Science Policy
- **Put** a “*seed in the ground*” by operationalizing the first recognised EOSC Node at the European level for the initial 3 years
- **Offer** “*core services*” for scientific research infrastructures to federate (single-sign-on, catalogues, knowledge graph, application workflow, monitoring, accounting, helpdesk) and common “*horizontal services*” for end-users to benefit from (compute, containers, data transfer, notebooks, file sharing, open research data)
- **Define** the *pathway and blueprint* (EOSC Interoperability Framework) for other potential EOSC Node operators to join the federation

Key questions for EOSC ENTRUST

- Is EOSC ENTRUST planning to provide “services” for the EOSC EU node?
 - E.g. registry of EU TREs?
- Is EOSC ENTRUST planning to share Data via the EOSC EU node?
- Is EOSC ENTRUST planning to use the resources of the EOSC Node (e.g. horizontal services)?
- Is EOSC ENTRUST planning to leverage on the Simpl middleware?

Latest news

- The EOSC EU Node will be operational in October 2024
- The official launch will be at the EOSC Symposium
- Unclear if there is going to be some testing during the summer

EOSC future post 2027

- Why a new governance?
 - The existing EOSC Co-Programmed Partnership terminates in 2030
 - Shortcomings have been identified with the current model (funding, coordination, representation)
- Who is involved in the decision making process?
 - EC (DG RTD & CNECT), EOSC-A Board of Directors, EOSC Steering Board (reprs of MSs and ACs)
- Where are we now?
 - Tasks to be sustained after 2027 identified: (EOSC Federation operation and expansion, broader FAIR activities, policies relevant to EOSC)
 - Analysis of different governance models ongoing (JU, 185, non institutionalized model)
- Timeline: Governance model to be selected by the end of 2024

What is the impact on EOSC ENTRUST?

- Future sustainability of projects' outputs (network, resources)
- Positioning of TRE related future developments in the EOSC Federation
- Positioning of TRE related future developments in the policy agenda

WP4-5-6 Comms, dissemination & outreach

Objectives/tasks

1. Develop and delivery a project **communication strategy**
2. Translate insights derived from technical work packages into accessible **policy recommendations** for decision makers
3. Outreach to **EOSC and the European Health Data Space (EHDS)**

Partners

ELIXIR Hub, HDR UK, CSC

WP4-5-6 Communication, dissemination & outreach

Task overview and effort

Mobilisation phase (Year 1)

1. Creation/delivery of communication & dissemination strategy, website & branding (ELIXIR Hub)
2. Creation and dissemination of policy briefs (HDRUK + ELIXIR Hub)

Fostering early adoption (Year 2)

1. TREs in EOSC/EHDS events (CSC + ELIXIR Hub)
2. Creation and dissemination of policy briefs (HDRUK + ELIXIR Hub)

Maximising impact (Year 3)

1. TREs in EOSC/EHDS events (CSC + ELIXIR Hub)
2. Summary brochure of EOSC ENTRUST outputs, stories and results (ELIXIR Hub)
3. Creation and dissemination of policy briefs (HDRUK + ELIXIR Hub)

WP4-5-6 Communication, dissemination & outreach

Deliverables and milestones

Deliverable	Who	Month
D2A.1 Dissemination, Communication & Exploitation Plan	ELIXIR	M6
D2A.2 Policy brief	HDR UK	M12
D2B.2 Policy brief	HDR UK	M24
D2C.3 Policy brief	HDR UK	M36
D2C.1 Summary brochure of technical outputs, results and stories	ELIXIR	M36

Milestone	Who	Month
M2A.1 <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Delivery of project logo, branding & templates	ELIXIR	M1
M2A.2 <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Delivery of (initial version of) project website	ELIXIR	M2
M2B.1 Outreach event to EOSC/EHDS	CSC/EUDAT	M13
M2C.1 Outreach event to EOSC/EHDS	CSC/EUDAT	M25

Task 1 - Communications and dissemination

Overview

Mobilisation phase (Year 1 - WP4)

- ✓ Set-up of communications channels - web, social, newsletter
- Creation of communication, dissemination and exploitation plan
- Implementation of communication plan, further development of website

Fostering early adoption (Year 2 - WP5)

- Implementation of comms plan - social media, news releases, website content

Maximising impact (Year 3 - WP6)

- Continued implementation of comms plan
- Creation of brochure of technical outputs and success stories

Task 1 - Communications and dissemination

Plans for first 6 months

	Milestone/Deliverable	Who	Month
M2A.1	✓ Delivery of project logo, branding and templates	ELIXIR	M1
M2A.2	✓ Delivery of project website	ELIXIR	M2
D2A.1	Dissemination, Communication & Exploitation Plan	ELIXIR	M6

- ✓ Branding - [Logo and slide templates](#)
- ✓ Social media ([LinkedIn](#) + [X](#))
- Quarterly project newsletters - [sign up](#)
- News releases ([launch](#))
- Ongoing development of [project website](#)

Task 1 - Communications and dissemination

Connections with other WPs

- Coordination and alignment
 - T1B.2 Strategic Alignment and contribution to the EOSC Partnership & other relevant initiatives
 - T1C.3 Exploitation & Long term Sustainability Plan Delivery
 - Internal project communications - supporting PMO to ensure project partners are aware of outcomes of Management Board meetings and release of deliverables & milestones
- All other WPs
 - Lead on communications of outcomes (social media, newsletter, website)
 - Support promotion of external events (training, meetings)
 - Support dissemination of technical outcomes (policy outreach/EOSC/EHDS outreach will also involve tasks 2 and 3)

Please tell us when

- You have outputs to communicate
- You need support with promotion or dissemination

Task 2 - Policy briefs

Overview

Mobilisation phase (Year 1 - WP4)

- Identification of relevant WPs and group meetings to inform first policy brief and messaging
- Translation of initial technical insights and recommendations in accessible format for key audiences
- M12 Deliverable: Baseline Policy Brief

Fostering early adoption (Year 2 - WP5)

- Consolidation of findings from technical alignment workshops, main outputs from drivers and key recommendations from the technical WPs
- M24 Deliverable: Second Policy Brief

Maximising impact (Year 3) - WP6)

- Finalise recommendations based on technical blueprint to inform national policies for implementation of secure and trusted research environment infrastructure
- Involvement of key stakeholders to refine final recommendations
- M36 Deliverable: Closing Policy Brief and dissemination

Task 2 - Policy briefs

Plans for first 6 months

	Milestone/Deliverable	Who	Month
M2A.1	Stakeholder engagement and initial interaction with technical WPs and Drivers	HDR UK	M1
M2A.2	Participation in relevant Driver and TRE Provider forum meetings	HDR UK	M3
D2A.1	Summarise preliminary insights from f3f Driver workshop and TRE provider forum meetings, to inform technical blueprint insights	HDR UK	M6

- Leveraging existing networks
- Sharing knowledge with relevant EU projects
- Building on existing work

Principles and best practice for TREs

HDRUK
Health Data Research UK

Informing UK Policy and investment

Informing European policy through Towards the Health Data Space project

eOSC | **ENTRUST**

European Network of Trusted Research Environments

<https://zenodo.org/records/5767586>

Task 2 - Policy briefs

Connections with other WPs

- Coordination and alignment (WP1-2-3)
 - T1A.3 Exploitation as a Route to Sustainability
 - T1B.3 Exploitation & Long-term Sustainability Mapping
 - T1C.3 Exploitation & Long term Sustainability Plan Delivery
- Drivers (WP7-8-9)
 - Driver requirements for TREs
- Providers (WP10-11-12)
 - TRE current capabilities
- Architecture (WP13-14-15)
- Technology (WP16-17-18)
- Workflow processing (WP19-20-21)

Task 3 - EOSC/EHDS outreach

This task will be responsible for promoting the early results of the project in the EOSC and EHDS context, and later on also expanding the scope of dissemination and communications activities to include other relevant European Data Spaces

Mobilisation phase (Year 1 - WP4)

- First milestone due M13 (outreach event to EOSC/EHDS)

Fostering early adoption (Year 2 - WP5)

- Contribution to EOSC and EHDS events
- Online workshop for stakeholders discussing early project results (M2B.1, due M13)

Maximising impact (Year 3) - WP6)

- Expanding scope of engagement to include also other Data Spaces
- Contributions to EOSC and Data Spaces annual events
- Second online workshop (M2C.1, due M25), results will feed into T1C.2 opinion paper

Task 3 - EOSC/EHDS outreach

Plans for first 6 months

- First milestone (M2B.1) outreach event to EOSC/EHDS is due M13
- Mapping out key EOSC and EHDS events in order to recognise opportunities for participation and co-location throughout the project
- Recognising people within EOSC-ENTRUST that have already close connections to EOSC and other data spaces
- New EOSC Association TF on Health Data key group to liaise with
- T1.2 (Strategic alignment and contribution to the EOSC partnership, EHDS and other relevant initiatives), also lead by CSC/EUDAT, will give valuable input for planning the first outreach event activities beyond

Task 3 - EOSC/EHDS outreach

Connections with other WPs

- Coordination and alignment (WP1)
 - T1.2 Strategic Alignment and contribution to the EOSC Partnership, EHDS & other relevant initiatives
- Drivers (WP3)
 - Mapping out links among drivers to EOSC and other data spaces
- Providers (WP4)
 - T4.4 Building TRE capabilities for EOSC (Lead: CSC/EUDAT)
 - T4.5 Requirement update and capability building for EOSC (Lead: CSC/EUDAT)
 - T4.7 Sustainability model for the TRE Provider Forum (Lead: Sigma2)
- Architecture (WP5), Technology (WP6), Workflow processing (WP7)
 - Results from these WP's to be reported at stakeholder workshops

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Funded by
the European Union

Trusted environments for sensitive data management in EOSC

18 & 19 March 2024

Project Governance

Funded by
the European Union

EOSC-ENTRUST Governance

- Advise the project as requested
 - To be established (5 members)
 - Nominations welcome until April 30th
- Responsible for the implementation of the project
 - Monthly meetings. Next May 6th - 11 AM CET
 - Coordination, monitoring (KPIs, activities) and **support**
 - Update general assembly quarterly, July 31st
- Decision making body
 - Beneficiaries get to vote on all decisions
 - Associated partners can't vote on financial aspects of the project as they do not receive EU funding
 - Suggestions for General Assembly 2025 meeting location welcome

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